

TEXTURAL ANALYSIS OF A ONE-DIMENSIONAL METAL-ORGANIC FRAMEWORK CATENA-[BIS (FORMATO) COPPER (II) DIMETHYLAMINE]N OBTAINED FROM NITROGEN ADSORPTION.

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The study of nitrogen adsorption properties of porous compounds provides important information about their textural and structural characteristics. The N₂ adsorption properties of the newly synthesized MOF are shown in Figure 1. The adsorption isotherm exhibited a steady increase from low to high relative pressure, with a sharp rise as it approached P/P₀=1. This indicates the presence of two types of nanopores in the adsorbent: a small amount of micropores and a large amount of mesopores. Along with Table 1 and Figure 2, it presents

Figure 1. Nitrogen adsorption isotherm of catena-[bis (formato) copper (II) dimethylamine]n

important indicators such as surface area, pore size, and their volume distribution. These parameters were determined using appropriate adsorption isotherm models. These results contribute significantly to understanding the textural properties of the adsorbent and are important for potential application areas.

Table 1 above provides important information about the textural properties of the porous metal-organic framework catena-[bis (formato) copper (II) dimethylamine]n and highlights its excellent surface characteristics. Specifically, the specific surface area (S_{BET}) is 352.31 m²/g, of which the mesopore area is 222.69 m²/g, demonstrating the metal-organic framework's efficiency in adsorbing numerous molecules. The mesopore volume, determined by the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method, is 0.973 cm³/g.

Figure 2. Volume histogram of catena-[bis (formato) copper (II) dimethylamine]n.

Table 1. Texture characteristics of catena-[bis (formato) copper (II) dimethylamine]n based on nitrogen adsorption	
$S_{BET}, m^2/g$	352,31
t-Plot Micropore Area, m^2/g	47,69
t-Plot external surface area, m^2/g	107,16
Cumulative surface area of mesopores (BJH), m^2/g	222,69
t-Plot micropore volume, cm^3/g	0,227
Mesopores cumulative volume, cm^3/g	0,973
Maximum pore volume (HK), cm^3/g	0,056
Average pore diameter ($4V/A$ by BET), Å	110,52
Median pore width, Å	16,37
Average pore hydraulic radius (V/A by MP method), Å	90,39

This indicates that the metal-organic framework is predominantly mesoporous, as it is characterized by a larger volume of mesopores compared to micropores. The volume of the largest pores (HK) is 0.0558 cm^3/g . Furthermore, the average pore radius, determined by the MP (micropore) method, is 90.39 Å. Figure 4.10 provides a detailed differential distribution of pores across the corresponding diameters in the analyzed metal-organic framework. It has been established that this adsorbent contains two distinct categories of pores: the recorded volume for pores with a diameter of 2-20 nanometers is approximately 0.227 cm^3/g . However, when examining pores larger than 2 nanometers in diameter, a consistent decrease in their distribution is observed. Their volume in the range of 7.0-20 nanometers was approximately 0.973 cm^3/g . This data on pore size distribution is crucial, as it significantly contributes to understanding the adsorption properties of the metal-organic framework and is therefore important for its application in numerous fields. These data on the pore size distribution are very important, as they make a

significant contribution to understanding the adsorption properties of the material-organic framework and are therefore important for its application in many areas.

